

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF ENLIGHTENERS OF THE XIX-XX CENTURIES

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Abstract: In this thesis, information is given about the modernist movement and its implications, and the pedagogical views and theories of modernist enlighteners are widely covered.

Key words: Jadid, methods, representatives of development, Turkish languages, Jadidism movement.

Introduction.

"The Jadidism movement, which arose in a number of eastern and Muslim countries at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, has deep historical roots in Turkestan. It should be noted that our country was not left out of these processes of great socio-political and educational importance, on the contrary, it became one of the centers of this movement. The Jadids, who were the leading figures of their time, came to the field with the idea of achieving national development by spreading knowledge and enlightenment, radically reforming the field of education in extremely difficult and difficult conditions. For this purpose, they established schools and theaters, publishing houses and libraries, newspapers and magazines at their own expense, and sent talented young people to study abroad. These noble initiatives and actions of theirs resonated strongly in the life of the society and became a powerful wave. I think that in our region, which was the site of two great renaissances in history, the third renaissance could be realized by our ancestors. Unfortunately, the authoritarian regime did not allow them to fully realize their noble ideas and practical actions. While we are building a free civil society and a legal democratic state in our country today, we rely on the humanistic views of our ancestors and draw spiritual strength from their legacy. Great work is being done in our country to perpetuate the memory of our ancestors who suffered political repression during the autocratic regime. August 31 is widely celebrated as the Day of Remembrance of Repression Victims. The "Martyrs' Memorial" memorial complex, the State Museum of the Memory of Repression Victims and its regional departments are operating. Many scientific studies, artistic works, and films are being created on the history of the Jadidism movement. Memorial complexes, educational institutions, museums, parks and avenues named after our great enlighteners are being built. Over the past three years, the names of more than four hundred compatriots who were victims of repression were acquitted by the

Supreme Court of Uzbekistan. It is particularly noteworthy that the majority of them are representatives of the Jadidist movement. Dear friends! We have made it a strategic task to create a new Renaissance foundation in our country in order to realize the sacred dreams of our enlightened grandfathers. For this purpose, we are implementing fundamental reforms in the fields of science, education and culture¹.

It is known that the movement of Jadids, whose activities are not only political, but also aimed at improving education and upbringing, spiritual and educational reform of the Turkestan country, and raising a mature generation, is its goal played an important role in the history of the peoples of the country. In fact, the word jadid (Arabic "jadid" - new) means renewal and is a socio-political and educational movement, which consists of applying new modern school, printing press, methods of national development to the society, the general name of the supporters of this trend. At the end of the 19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century, Jadidism was formed as the national ideology of the national liberation movement in Turkestan, as the idea of national independence and enlightenment of the peoples of the country. Behbudi, Fitrat, Cholpon, Munavvar Qori, Abdulla Avloniy, the progressive representatives of the Jadidism movement, which became famous in the 19th century with the ideas of enlightenment and developed in the beginning of the 20th century, became stronger in their work and activity. Jadids put forward the idea of unifying the peoples of Turkestan and fighting for the national independence of the whole country. Turkestan Jadids carried out huge cultural works in order to raise the social-political, cultural-educational life, consciousness level of the local population of Turkestan, including the growing youth, who fell into a backward situation due to the tyranny of the tsarist government. As Mahmudhoja Behbudi noted, "In each country, as the youth of that country started to take the initiative and the tool of reform and culture, our school, which is at the door of culture in Turkestan, is the harbinger of renaissance and reform from the beginning". "The national press, the movement of brave young people came into being in the shadow of the guardians of education." The doctrine of the ancients was the true doctrine of its time. Because he can lead not only progressive people, but also thinking young people. Jadids stressed that young adults should grow up to be fighters for the future and development of Turkestan, and they stress that they will get rid of all kinds of evils by doing so.

¹ Sh. Mirziyoyev: Greetings to the participants of the international conference dedicated to the study of the heritage of the ancients. March 6, 2023.

In order to raise healthy children, they emphasized that they should be knowledgeable, enlightened, and most importantly, parents should help their children acquire modern sciences in time. Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov spoke about the responsibility of the parents in the education and upbringing of the child and emphasized that there are those who try their best to make their child enlightened. Jadids emphasized that parents are involved in the education of their children and prepare them for schools and madrasas. After studying and graduating from schools and madrasas, young people should improve their knowledge in educational institutions of developed countries and acquire modern sciences. During the old regime, we did not know our history. In a word, it was a time when we cried not for our stomachs, but for our values. Self-awareness means knowing our history, our thousand-year-old traditions. If every person knows the past, he will never repeat the same mistake. Remember, once upon a time, during the communist ideology, it was impossible to even go to a funeral, let alone develop national customs and traditions. Look, what a hard time it was! If we explain this truth to our children, if we arm ourselves with history and truth, we will set our lives on the right path, and its exact destinations will be clear to everyone, give strength to our whole nation is working. It means a free, liberated, peaceful and stable, prosperous and prosperous life. The old people also paid special attention to the idea that it is necessary to pay special attention to the education of the young generation at school. Because the moderns look at the young generation as those who fought for freedom, independence, and the future and development of the Motherland. That is why they pay special attention to the issue of children and the fate of the Motherland. It should be noted that, through their schools, the Jadids tried to instill not only the national spirit, but also universal human value, internationalism, prosperity and beauty of the Motherland into the young generation. It is not just a school for the education of children and young people, but they have learned that they should independently get acquainted with the events of the time and the world, be aware of the state of the nation and the Motherland, and daily life.

“... In the next six years, the number of pre-school educational organizations in our republic increased almost 6 times, from 4988 to 29420, and the number of higher educational institutions increased from 77 to 213. New types of presidential schools, creativity schools, and specialized schools are being established in our country. The intelligence, will and tenacity of our progressive ancestors serve as a model school for all of us in raising our children

to become people who are well-rounded, loyal to national and universal values. We consider it an urgent task to further study the activities of modern scientists in cooperation with international scientific centers and world scientists. Through this unique heritage, we can find correct answers to many questions that concern humanity today. The more we actively promote this priceless wealth, the more our people, especially our youth, will realize the value of today's peaceful and free life. I wish all participants of the conference good health, new creative achievements, and success in the work of the conference."²

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it can be said that Jadidism served as the main factor in the national, cultural and social awakening and development of the youth of Turkestan. In their articles and works, the moderns showed the ways to solve the current issues of the time, the problems of life in a social-political, cultural-spiritual way. It invites young people to study, to engage in the process of acquiring knowledge and production, to raise their cultural and spiritual level. In the desire to bring the achievements of world development to Turkestan, mature scientists who serve the Motherland, modern scholars, specialists of the fields of industry and agriculture, and cultural figures have emerged from them, believing that they will make the country prosperous and prosperous. Modern ideas about protecting the interests of young people and creating appropriate opportunities for them to occupy a worthy place in society and the state are reflected in today's New Uzbekistan.

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